

1 Characterization and functionality of fructo-oligosaccharides affecting water status of
2 strawberry fruit (*Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois) during postharvest storage

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24 **Abstract**

25 Water status and analyses of free sugars, sugar-alcohols and fructo-oligosaccharides
26 (FOS) were carried out in *Fragaria x vesca* treated with different high CO₂
27 concentrations applied to minimize damage caused by storage at 0 °C. The
28 thermodynamic parameters such as the amount of unfrozen water (U_w), T_g, T_g' , and
29 peak position of the O-H stretching vibration were determined in various saccharides
30 including FOS (1-kestose, nystose and kestopentaose) by infrared spectroscopy studies
31 and differential scanning calorimetry. Beneficial high CO₂ treatment (20%) avoided the
32 reduction of unfreezable water fraction and increased endogenous FOS levels, in
33 contrast to that observed in air-stored and in those exposed to higher CO₂ levels (40%).
34 The direct FOS-water interaction, possibly within the hydrogen-bond network of
35 cellular structures, could explain the maintenance of water status, cell integrity and the
36 low water leakage levels in 20% CO₂-treated fruit at values similar to those found in
37 freshly harvested fruit.

38

39 **Keywords:** Fructo-oligosaccharides, polyols, strawberry, water status, microstructure,
40 high CO₂, low temperature.

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42 **1. Introduction**

43 Strawberries are highly perishable fruit susceptible to water loss and pathogen attack.
44 Consequently, many approaches have been undertaken to improve strawberry
45 postharvest storage procedures in order to maintain fruit quality. Most of the work has
46 focused on the beneficial effect of low temperature and gaseous treatments in
47 controlling storage decay in different varieties of *Fragaria x ananassa*. The effect of
48 high CO₂ treatments on the quality of strawberries has been extensively analysed

49 through changes in colour, titratable acidity, pH, soluble solids and phenolic compounds
50 (Gil, Holcroft, & Kader, 1997; Bodelón, Blanch, Sanchez-Ballesta, Escribano, &
51 Merodio, 2010). However, the molecular mechanism behind the protective role of high
52 CO₂ levels is still not well understood. It has been reported that in other highly
53 perishable fruit such as grapes, high CO₂ levels induced the accumulation of FOS during
54 low temperature storage (Blanch, Sanchez-Ballesta, Escribano, & Merodio, 2011). FOS
55 is a common name for fructose oligomers that are composed mainly of kestose, nystose,
56 and kestopentaose, in which fructosyl units are bound by a β linkage at the position of
57 sucrose and in which the degree of polymerization is less than 5. There are many
58 positive aspects related to the presence of fructans in plants. Indeed, they have been
59 implicated in abiotic stress-tolerance and they might provide protection from damage to
60 cytosolic proteins and cell membranes (Valluru, & Van den Ende, 2008). However,
61 there is little or no thermodynamic information about FOS or comparative studies with
62 other simple saccharides that could explain their protective action against stress
63 conditions.

64 Fructans may also have functions like carbon storage, and their synthesis results from
65 extended sucrose metabolism. With respect to soluble sugars and starch, variations have
66 been observed in the amount and type of carbohydrates accumulated in fruit both
67 between and within genotypes of a species (Nardoza et al., 2011). Moreover, sugar-
68 alcohols (polyols) are a group of naturally occurring carbohydrate derivatives that, in
69 addition to other roles, function in the interconversion of some monosaccharides. It has
70 been reported that *myo*-inositol can be found in most fruit and vegetables, whereas the
71 presence of sorbitol and/or mannitol was related to each species. Specifically, sorbitol is
72 known to be a major constituent of leaves and fruit of the *Rosaceous* species, and can be
73 an important translocating compound in this species. As carbohydrates and sugar-

74 alcohols have similar structures, they are difficult to separate by conventional reversed-
75 phase liquid chromatography, therefore the amperometric detection method was used
76 (Cataldi, Margiotta, & Zambonin, 1998). This method was also used to successfully
77 quantify FOS in accumulating and non-accumulating fructan species during storage
78 (Ishiguro, Onodera, Benkeblia, & Shiomi, 2010; Blanch et al., 2011).

79 Furthermore, the accumulation of saccharides in plants can contribute to both the water
80 potential (ψ_w) and the protection of macromolecular structures against the destabilizing
81 effects of decreasing water activity and/or low temperature storage (Popp & Smirnov,
82 1995). We previously reported changes in water status during ripening and storage in
83 different kinds of fruit, where specifically high CO₂ treatment caused a marked increase
84 in the unfreezable water fraction (Goñi, Fernandez-Caballero, Sanchez-Ballesta,
85 Escribano, & Merodio, 2011). The unfreezable, bound or structured water in living
86 tissue is more likely to play a major role in stress tolerance by maintaining the structural
87 integrity and/or cell wall extensibility, while an increased amount of free water might be
88 able to enhance solute accumulation, leading to better osmotic adjustment and
89 maintenance of the volumes of sub-cellular compartments.

90 In the present study, our principal aims were to analyse how different high CO₂
91 treatments during low temperature storage improve: 1) the turnover of nonstructural
92 carbohydrates (glucose, fructose and sucrose), polyols (*myo*-inositol, D-sorbitol and D-
93 mannitol) and FOS, using high-performance anion-exchange chromatography with
94 integrated pulsed amperometric detection (HPAEC-PAD), 2) the thermodynamical
95 properties of FOS using infrared spectroscopy studies and differential scanning
96 calorimetry, and 3) the physiological characterization of fruit tissue in terms of changes in
97 water potential (ψ_w) and unfreezable water content. Moreover, in order to establish the

98 tolerance limits to high CO₂ concentrations, different treatments (3 days with 20% and
99 40% CO₂) were applied.

100 **2. Material and Methods**

101 **2.1 Plant material**

102 Organic remontant strawberries (*Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois) harvested from
103 the first flowering from Monjarama orchard, San Sebastian de los Reyes, Madrid
104 (Spain) were stored at 0 °C (± 0.5) in three sealed containers with a capacity of 1 m³.
105 Ten plastic boxes of about 1 kg of strawberries per box were stored in each container for
106 3 days, with a continuous flow of air or gas mixture containing 20% CO₂ or 40% CO₂.
107 The same O₂ concentration (20%) was maintained in all three lots. Initially, and at the
108 end of the treatments (3 days), 45 strawberries from five boxes were removed at random
109 from each of the treatment groups, frozen in liquid nitrogen and then stored at -80 °C for
110 further analysis.

111 **2.2. Extraction and chromatographic determination of sugars, polyols and fructo-** 112 **oligosaccharides**

113 To determine sugars (glucose, fructose and sucrose) and polyols (*myo*-inositol, D-
114 sorbitol, and D-mannitol), 1 g of each sample was homogenized in 5 ml of ultra-pure
115 water and centrifuged at 30,000g for 20 min, after which the supernatants were filtered
116 through a 0.45 µm pore size membrane. The determination of these compounds was
117 carried out by HPAEC-PAD, equipped with a Metrosep Carb 1-250 IC column (4.6 x
118 250 mm) as described by Bodelón et al.,(2010). The content of each sugar was
119 expressed as mg/g fresh weight (FW) of the sample, each polyol as mg/g FW for *myo*-
120 inositol, and µg/g FW for D-sorbitol and D-mannitol, and the data produced were the
121 means of the three replicates, two different measurements being made.

122 The quantification of nystose, nystose b and kestopentaose and that of 1-kestose and
123 neokestose, which required pre-treatment with an activated carbon Darco G60, 100
124 mesh (Sigma, Steinheim, Germany) to remove the mono- and disaccharides, was
125 determined following the method of Blanch et al., (2011). Briefly, the samples were
126 extracted with 85% ethanol, boiled under reflux and centrifuged at 5,000g for 20 min at
127 4 °C. The supernatant was evaporated and then redissolved with deionised water,
128 filtered through 0.22 µm filters and analysed by HPAEC-PAD equipped with a
129 CarboPac PA1 carbohydrate column. A three-step PAD protocol was used and the
130 samples (1.5 ml) were injected using an autosampler (model, 838 Advanced Sample
131 Processor, Metrohm, Herisau, Switzerland). FOS identification was performed by
132 comparing the retention time of standard mixtures (1-kestose and nystose from Sigma,
133 Steinheim, Germany, and kestopentaose from Megazyme, Co.Wicklow, Ireland) with
134 those reported in publications, and the FOS content was expressed as µg/g FW of the
135 sample.

136 **2.3. Determination of water status**

137 The total water content (g/100 g FW) was determined after a stable weight had been
138 obtained after drying at 105 °C. Drip loss was determined by a method adapted from
139 Lowithum and Charoenrein (2009). Frozen strawberry samples were stored at -20 °C for
140 4 and 9 days and then the tissues were thawed at 8 °C for 1 h before measuring drip loss.
141 Strawberry tissue ψ_w was measured by a Dewpoint PotentialMeter, WP4, (Decagon
142 Devices, Inc. USA). ψ_w measurements were repeatedly taken from a 2 mm thick
143 strawberry disc cut from the middle portion of four strawberries. ψ_w of untreated and
144 CO₂-treated strawberries was determined at the onset of low temperature storage.
145 Calibration was at 25 °C with KCl standard (-2.22 MPa).

146 The unfreezable water content was determined in frozen pulverized strawberry pulp
147 tissues (10-20 mg) using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC822e, Mettler-Toledo
148 Inc. USA) equipped with a liquid nitrogen cooling accessory, following the method of
149 Goñi, Escribano, & Merodio (2008). Indium, deionized water and zinc were used for
150 calibration, and an empty aluminium pan was used as the reference. Samples were
151 placed in 100 μ L aluminium pans which were hermetically sealed and a method based
152 on fusion heat was used to calculate the amount of unfreezable water content.

153 **2.4. Thermodynamic characterization of FOS**

154 **2.4.1. Determination of glass transition temperatures of the different anhydrous** 155 **sugars**

156 A DSC822e Mettler-Toledo differential scanning calorimeter was also used to
157 determine the glass transition temperatures (T_g) for the anhydrous sugar glasses.
158 Samples (10-15 mg) were placed in 40 μ L hermetically sealed aluminium pans. To
159 remove any residual water from the samples, a pinhole was made in the sealed pan and
160 a preheating gradient was used from 25 $^{\circ}$ C to 100 $^{\circ}$ C at 2 $^{\circ}$ C/min. During preheating, a
161 dry helium gas was streamed at 100 ml/min to prevent condensation of moisture within
162 the DSC furnace. The dried amorphous sugar was prepared by heating each crystalline
163 compound from -10 $^{\circ}$ C to a temperature above melting point at 10 $^{\circ}$ C min^{-1} . Then,
164 samples were cooled to -10 $^{\circ}$ C at 100 $^{\circ}$ C/min and left at this temperature for 5 min. In
165 order to erase the thermal history of the sugar, each sample was subjected to a further
166 three heating and cooling cycles. For all samples, the midpoint of the deflection in the
167 heat flow versus temperature curve was taken as the T_g .

168 **2.4.2. Determination of the amount of unfrozen water of the different sugars.**

169 The anti-freeze characteristics of the different sugars were evaluated calorimetrically
170 by the amount of unfrozen water (U_w) and ice glass transition temperatures (T_g') as

171 described by Furuki (2002), but with slight differences using a DSC822e (Mettler-
172 Toledo, USA). Aqueous solutions of sugar at desired concentrations were prepared by
173 weighing with deionized distilled water. Sugar concentration was gradually changed
174 from 5 weight % up to a maximum of 50 weight %. A series of prepared aqueous
175 solutions were sealed in independent vials and kept at 25 °C for 24 h in an incubator to
176 allow them to reach a steady state.

177 Aqueous samples (5-10 µl) placed in 40 µl hermetically sealed aluminium pans were
178 cooled from 25 °C to -80 °C at 10 °C/min. The samples were left at this temperature for
179 5 min and then heated to 25 °C at 10 °C/min. The heating scan was used to determine
180 the latent heat of the melting ice (ΔH_m) by integration of the melting endotherm and the
181 T_g ' by the deflection midpoint in the heat flow versus temperature curve. U_w , was
182 determined by extrapolating ΔH_m , which was linearly dependent on sugar concentration

183183 (weight %), to zero as follows:

184184
$$U_w = \frac{M_r (H_2O)}{\frac{100 - C'_s}{C'_s}}$$

185185
$$M_r (sugar)$$

186 where C'_s is the sugar concentration of the freeze-concentrated liquid fraction ($\Delta H_m =$
187 0) expressed in wt. %, $M_r (H_2O)$ the molecular mass of deionized water (18.02 g/mol)
188 and $M_r (sugar)$ the molecular mass of the different sugars.

189 **2.4.3. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy of the different sugar glasses**

190 Dried amorphous sugars obtained during the determination of T_g were placed on the
191 surface of a Spectrum-400 Perkin Elmer ATR-FTIR (Perkin Elmer, USA). The
192 complete absence of residual water from the sugar samples was confirmed by the
193 disappearance of the water IR band at around 1645 cm^{-1} . For each IR spectrum, 64
194 scans were obtained over the range 650-4000 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} . The

195 spectra were analysed using Spectrum software, to determine the peak position of the O-
196 H stretching vibration (ν_{OH}).

197 **2.5. Low temperature scanning electron microscopy of the strawberry structure.**

198 A 5 mm thick median-transverse slice from each strawberry fruit was cut and frozen
199 and then a sector was analysed using a Zeiss DSN-960 electron scanning microscope,
200 equipped with a cold stage Cryostrans CT-1500 (Oxford Instruments). Frozen tissue
201 sectors were cryofractured at $-180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, etched at $-90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, gold-coated and subsequently
202 transferred to the microscope where observations was carried out at -150 to $-160\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.
203 Samples were observed with both secondary and retro-dispersed electrons, and the best
204 images were selected in each case.

205 **2.6. Statistical analysis**

206 One-way ANOVA and correlational analyses were employed using SPSS ver. 19.0.
207 The multicomparison of means was assessed by Bonferroni's test, to determine the level
208 of significance at $p < 0.05$. The main effects of CO_2 treatment, storage time, and x
209 treatment time interaction on strawberry fruit were analyzed.

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211 **3. Results**

212 **3.1. Simple sugars, polyols and water status in air-stored organic strawberry fruit** 213 **or treated with different high CO_2 concentrations during storage at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.**

214 The sugar and polyol concentrations and water status parameters assessed in air-
215 stored (3 days) strawberries or treated with 20 and 40% CO_2 for 3 days are compared
216 with non-stored (day 0, freshly harvested) fruit in Table 1. It can be seen that the
217 absolute values of the monosaccharides in the strawberries were similar to those found
218 for the disaccharide sucrose. The sucrose concentration in this variety of strawberries is
219 high and can reach values of 20 mg/g FW . The content of sucrose significantly

220 decreased in air-stored strawberries, reaching an average value 29% less than in fruit
221 treated with 20% CO₂. Moreover, the sucrose content in these treated fruits was similar
222 to that found in non-stored fruit. The content of both glucose and fructose were also
223 higher in CO₂-treated strawberries than in untreated fruit.

224 With regards to the content of polyols in freshly harvested fruit, it is worth noting that
225 the high *myo*-inositol content, reached values of 0.22 mg/g FW, while the D-sorbitol
226 levels in this variety belonging to the *Rosaceae* family were 29.31 µg/g FW and those
227 of D-mannitol 1.16 µg/g FW. The high levels of *myo*-inositol were maintained in all lots
228 and non-significant differences were quantified. However it is necessary to emphasize
229 that there was only a significant increase in D-sorbitol content in 3 day 20% CO₂
230 strawberries. The low levels of D-mannitol only varied slightly.

231 Water status was also assessed during storage at 0 °C in air-stored strawberry fruit and
232 fruit treated with 20 and 40% CO₂ for 3 days and compared with non-stored fruit (Table
233 1). While similar values of total moisture content were quantified in all lots, the ψ_w was
234 observed to vary between fruit kept in air (0.03% CO₂) and fruit treated with high CO₂
235 levels. The results indicated that low temperature storage produced an increase in ψ_w
236 from -2.60 MPa found in non-stored fruit to -1.93 MPa in air-treated fruit stored for 3
237 days at 0 °C, although the sharpest rise in water potential took place in strawberries
238 treated with 40% CO₂ for 3 days. Furthermore, as shown in Table 1 in both air-treated
239 and 40% CO₂-treated tissues a significant decrease in the unfreezable water content was
240 detected, although the levels were substantially lower in the latter, reaching the lowest
241 values (0.79 g/g DW), whereas in non-stored fruit, the unfreezable water fraction and
242 ψ_w in 20% CO₂-treated fruit remained unchanged. As for freezing and structural
243 integrity, which is manifested through exudate or drip loss at thawing, our results shown
244 in Table 1, indicated that treatment with 20% CO₂ levels for 3 days prevented the drip

245 loss of strawberries frozen at -20 °C for 4 days, and the only significant increase from
246 1.34 to 1.65 was detected after 9 days. The sharpest rise in drip loss values was
247 quantified in air-stored tissues that reached values 2.6 times higher than in freshly
248 harvested fruit tissues, followed by 3 day 40% CO₂ treated strawberries with values 1.8
249 times higher.

250 **3.2. Identification and quantification of FOS in air-stored organic strawberry fruit** 251 **or treated with different high CO₂ concentrations during storage at 0°C.**

252 The FOS identified by HPAEC-PAD analysis in non-stored (day 0), air-stored (3
253 day), 3-day 20% CO₂-treated and 3-day 40% CO₂-treated strawberries are shown in
254 Figure 1. Each size class of fructan is composed of more than one isomer, and the
255 following isomers in the strawberries are identified as follows: for DP3, 1-kestose (3a)
256 and neokestose (3b), in the case of DP4, nystose (4c) and nystose b (4b) and for DP5,
257 kestopentaose (5a). The higher DP isomers in strawberries have not yet been quantified
258 but the chromatogram indicated variations in the pattern or distribution between the
259 different lots with high levels in 20% CO₂ fruit, as well as higher accumulations of high
260 DP fructans in strawberries under different storage conditions. In Figure 1 we can see a
261 mixture of both high DP and low DP fructans.

262 The content of identified FOS is shown in Fig. 2. Levels of 43.85 µg kestose/g FW were
263 reached in freshly harvested fruit, and these levels increased significantly in 20% CO₂-
264 treated strawberries (Fig. 2A). The highest amounts were reached in these treated fruits,
265 whereas those observed in treated fruit with 40% CO₂ were similar to that found in non-
266 stored fruit. The neokestose content (Fig. 2B) was approximately a quarter of the 1-
267 kestose content. Moreover no significant changes were observed in fruit during storage
268 at 0 °C with and without CO₂ treatments. With respect to nystose levels (Fig. 2C), we
269 also observed a significant increase in 20% CO₂-treated strawberries, which were the

270 highest compared with air-stored and 40% CO₂-treated fruit. The levels of nystose b
271 (Fig. 2D) followed the same pattern as neokestose, being ten times lower than nystose,
272 consistent with the activation of the inulin-series synthesis pathway. In the case of
273 kestopentaose (Fig. 2E), the same pattern can be observed with higher levels in 20%
274 CO₂-treated strawberries, although there was also an increase in air-stored fruit.

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276 **3.3. Analysis of microstructure of air-stored organic strawberry fruit and fruit** 277 **treated with different high CO₂ concentrations during storage at 0 °C.**

278 LT-SEM micrographs of fractured strawberry tissues during storage at 0 °C were
279 obtained from both non-stored (day 0) and air-stored (3 days) fruit, as well as from fruit
280 treated with 20 and 40% CO₂ for 3 days. As can be seen in Figure 3, the non-stored
281 strawberries (Fig. 3A) contained cells that exhibited a typical cell morphology, whereas
282 air-stored fruits (Fig. 3B) exhibited an increased cell volume and deteriorated structure.
283 In the case of CO₂-treated fruit, the cell structure was better formed, more compact and
284 better organized in 20% CO₂-treated fruit (Fig. 3C) than in those treated with 40% (Fig.
285 3D). In 20% CO₂-treated fruit, the tissues contained cells which had maintained their
286 integrity, with regular contours and intercellular spaces filled with air. By contrast,
287 extracellular liquid was observed in tissues treated with 40% CO₂ for 3 days, indicating
288 that membrane and cell wall disruption was advanced. In addition, the micrographs
289 revealed that low temperature storage at 0 °C in air produced the largest cells and a high
290 degree of tissue disorganization (Fig. 3B).

291 **3.4. Thermodynamic characterization of FOS**

292 The thermal characterization by differential scanning calorimetry and the results of
293 infrared spectroscopy studies of FOS (1-kestose, nystose and kestopentaose), sugars
294 (glucose, trehalose, maltotriose, maltotetraose, fructose, sucrose and raffinose) are

295 shown in Table 2. The thermodynamic parameters include: the amount of unfrozen
296 water (U_w), the ice-glass transition temperatures (T_g'), the glass transition temperatures
297 of anhydrous carbohydrates (T_g) and the peak position of the O-H stretching vibration
298 (ν_{OH}). The values obtained have been compared with those reported by other authors
299 and are given in (Table 2), with the exception of FOS for which there are no previous
300 data. The tetrasaccharide, maltotetraose, had the highest T_g (134.30) followed in order
301 by the trisaccharides (raffinose, maltotriose), the disaccharides (trehalose and sucrose)
302 and finally the monosaccharides (glucose and fructose). In the case of FOS,
303 kestopentaose had the highest T_g value (120.85) followed by nystose (102.17) and 1-
304 kestose (91.16). Interestingly, a positive upward slope between T_g and U_w was obtained.
305 However, a different behaviour was observed between glucose and fructose
306 oligosaccharides (Fig. 4A). Although the shift from the disaccharide sucrose to
307 maltotriose was accompanied by an increase in the water content from 7.60 to 13.66
308 mol H₂O/mol solute, in the case of 1-kestose the change in the quantity of U_w was 29%
309 greater, reaching values of 17.58 mol H₂O/mol solute. Furthermore, nystose had a
310 higher value (18.94) than maltotetraose (14.31) and kestopentaose reached a value of
311 29.02 mol H₂O/mol solute. Moreover, although the correlation between U_w and
312 molecular weight was negligible, a good correlation was observed between U_w and the
313 number of furanose rings ($R^2 = 0.8168$) (Fig. 4B). In this Figure, as maltotriose and
314 maltotetraose had zero furanose residues their values were the lowest, followed by
315 raffinose with one furanose residue, 1-kestose with two, nystose with three and
316 kestopentaose with four furanose rings. Table 2 also lists the T_g' for the simple sugars
317 and oligosaccharides and compares them with already published values. It is significant
318 that there are marked differences in the T_g' value of FOS even though the molecular
319 weights are identical to saccharides other than FOS. Kestopentaose has the lowest T_g'

320 values, nystose has a T_g ' that is around 10 °C lower than that of maltotetraose and 1-
321 kestose has a T_g ' significant lower than that of raffinose and maltotriose. With the
322 exception of raffinose, the T_g ' values measured in this study are quite similar to those
323 reported in other publications.

324 In this work we have also studied the hydrogen-bonding interactions that take place in
325 carbohydrates of different chain lengths and with different T_g values, and the value of
326 ν_{OH} is indicated in Table 2. In all cases, the O-H stretching band is a broad band, with an
327 absorbance maximum at approximately 3300 cm^{-1} . It is evident that the O-H band shifts
328 to a higher wave number with increasing T_g (Fig. 4C) and a strong correlation is
329 obtained ($R^2 = 0.9579$).

330

331 **4. Discussion**

332 The amounts and types of the main carbohydrates in fruit vary. For instance, in table
333 grapes and strawberries soluble sugars are predominant, whereas in other fruit such as
334 banana, apple, pear, cherimoya and kiwifruit it is starch (Nardozza et al., 2011; Goñi et
335 al., 2008). In wild strawberries (*Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois) the sucrose content
336 is present in similar high concentrations to that of reducing sugars, and the FOS values
337 were higher than those reported for other vegetables and fruit (Muir, Shepherd, Rosella,
338 Barret, & Gibson, 2007). In the present work we observed (Table 1) a significant
339 decrease of sucrose in air-stored strawberries after 3 days of storage at 0 °C, contrary to
340 that indicated in 3-day 20% CO₂-treated fruit. Several studies have reported that the
341 accumulation of carbohydrates is involved in protecting plants against cold stress,
342 although controversial results have been indicated (Holland, Sala, Menezes, & Lafuente,
343 1999). The observed sucrose decrease in air-stored fruits could be due to a possible
344 breakdown into simple sugars but, such as the decrease was not concomitant with an

345 increase in glucose, fructose or sorbitol, it could suggest its preferential utilization for
346 respiration instead of for sugar interconversion. However, only in 20% CO₂-treated
347 strawberries a significant increase in D-sorbitol was quantified. In addition to the
348 possibly protective properties of this alditol (see references therein, Merchant and
349 Richter, 2011), in 20% CO₂-treated strawberries the increase in D-sorbitol may play
350 role in facilitating hexose metabolism, specifically in relation to FOS accumulation. In
351 this sense, the significant increase in 1-kestose, nystose and kestopentaose seems to
352 confirm that fructose is further metabolized into FOS. An increase in inulin-type
353 fructans was also observed in CO₂-table grapes (Blanch et al., 2011). It is worth noting
354 that despite the differences between these two types of fruit, there is a common response
355 in this carbon metabolism pathway, suggesting that beneficial high CO₂ treatment could
356 produce a similar response in different types of fruit.

357 Our results indicate that 20% CO₂ treatment maintained the water status of fruit at
358 levels similar to those found in freshly harvested fruit, with a control of both ψ_w and
359 unfreezable water fraction. In contrast, storage in air led to a marked decrease in
360 unfreezable water fraction accompanied by an increase in ψ_w . However, it was the 40%
361 CO₂-treated fruit that exhibited the highest increase in ψ_w concomitant with a marked
362 decrease in unfreezable water levels. It has been reported that pre-treatment with
363 salicylic acid applied to provide protection against salinity stress in tomato plants
364 caused a decrease in leaf ψ_w (Szepesi, et al., 2009), and that variations in ψ_w values were
365 observed during development of postharvest peel pitting in grape fruit (Alferez,
366 Alquezar, Burns & Zacarias, 2010).

367 According to these results, this study have given rise to important questions, namely,
368 whether the water status in strawberries with different FOS pattern accumulations could
369 be explained by their FOS thermodynamic properties. In this regard, several studies of

370 strawberries have been published dealing with the glass transition of freeze-dried
371 samples equilibrated to different moisture contents (Moraga, Martínez-Navarrete, &
372 Chiralt, 2004), and modifications of the glass transition temperature of frozen juice
373 samples by the addition of different carbohydrates (Torreggiani et al., 1999). With
374 regard to inulin, a polydisperse substance with an average DP of 25, the effect of
375 moisture content on the crystallinity of the glass transition temperature of standard high
376 performance inulin has been published (Zimeri & Kokini, 2002). Nevertheless, it is
377 important to note that in this study the results obtained for the thermal properties of
378 inulin-type fructans, with a degree of polymerization less than 5, were determined for
379 the first time. These results (Table 2 and Fig.4) provide evidence of an U_w increase in
380 the aqueous solution of FOS when compared with both aqueous oligosaccharides with
381 similar molecular weights and simple sugars. Kestopentaose, with the highest number of
382 furanose rings, reached values of 29.02 mol H₂O/mol solute, markedly higher than the
383 7.60 mol H₂O/mol solute of sucrose. In this context, FOS clearly shows a high ability to
384 bind water molecules. Additionally, a positive correlation was found between T_g and
385 U_w (Fig. 4A) although, a different behaviour observed between glucose and fructose
386 oligosaccharides, the latter showing the lower T_g values. Different flexibility and
387 degree of hydrogen bonding of hexose rings as compared with pentose rings has been
388 reported (Miller, & de Pablo, 2000). Furthermore, a very strong positive correlation was
389 observed between v_{OH} and T_g ($R^2 = 0.9579$) (Fig. 4), in good agreement with which has
390 been reported for other sugars (Wolkers, Oliver, Tablin, & Crowe, 2004). Moreover,
391 FOS exhibited the highest T_g ' values (Table 2). Our results suggest a direct relationship
392 between the molecular structure of FOS and their capacity to alter water behavior at
393 subzero temperatures. Consequently, through FOS induction by 20% CO₂ treatment,
394 strawberries could be more suitable for the freezing process and may explain the lower

395 exudate loss in 20% CO₂-treated fruit compared with air-stored fruit and 40% CO₂-
396 treated fruit (Table 1). Furthermore, in 20% CO₂-treated fruit cryo-SEM analysis
397 indicated that there was no evidence of cell structure damage, and cell volume was
398 maintained. Changes in cytoplasmic volume in *Arabidopsis* leaves at low growth
399 temperatures have been reported (Strand et al., 1999). Conversely, high water leakage
400 and a marked decrease in unfreezable water content were observed in 40% CO₂-treated
401 strawberries that had lower FOS levels. Hitmi, Coudret, Barthomeuf and Sallanon
402 (2000), demonstrated that in the cryopreservation of plant cells, using a carbohydrate
403 like sucrose as a protectant, the concomitant increased unfrozen water content in cells
404 was a key factor behind their enhanced survival during frozen storage.

405 Our study has revealed the usefulness of reliable identification and quantification of
406 polyols and FOS in non-fructan accumulating plant species as fruit, to understanding
407 adaptive responses to storage conditions.

408 In conclusion, non-stressful 20% CO₂ treatment avoids the reduction of unfreezable
409 water content and induces selective FOS in strawberries during storage at 0 °C.
410 Moreover, our results indicate that water status in 20% CO₂-treated fruit can be
411 explained, in part, by the specific hydration properties of these polymer furanose units.
412 This protective effect might be an important strategy for preventing damage caused by
413 storage at suboptimal low temperature.

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421 References

422 Alferez, F., Alquezar, B., Burns, J.K. & Zacarias, L. (2010). Variation in water, osmotic
423 and turgor potential in peel of 'Marsh' grapefruit during development of
424 postharvest peel pitting. *Postharvest Biology and Technology*, 56(1), 44-49.

425 Blanch, M., Sanchez-Ballesta, M. T., Escribano, M. I., & Merodio, C. (2011). Fructo-
426 oligosaccharides in table grapes and response to storage. *Food Chemistry*, 129,
427 724 -730.

428 Bodelón, O., Blanch, M., Sanchez-Ballesta, M. T., Escribano, M. I., & Merodio, C.
429 (2010). The effects of high CO₂ levels on anthocyanin composition, antioxidant
430 activity and soluble sugar content of strawberries stored at low non-freezing
431 temperature. *Food Chemistry*, 122, 673–678.

432 Cataldi, T. R. I., Margiotta, G., & Zambonin, C. G. (1998). Determination of sugars and
433 alditols in food samples by HPAEC with integrated pulsed amperometric
434 detection using alkaline eluents containing barium or strontium ions. *Food*
435 *Chemistry*, 62, 109-115.

436 Furuki, T. (2000). Effect of stereochemistry on the anti-freeze characteristics of
437 carbohydrates. A thermal study of aqueous monosaccharides at subzero
438 temperatures. *Carbohydrate. Research*, 323, 185–191.

439 Furuki, T. (2002). Effects of molecular structure on thermodynamic properties of
440 carbohydrates. A calorimetric study of aqueous di- and oligosaccharides at
441 subzero temperatures. *Carbohydrate Research*, 337, 441-450.

442 Gil, M. I., Holcroft., D. M., & Kader, A. A. (1997). Changes in Strawberry
443 Anthocyanins and Other Polyphenols in Response to Carbon Dioxide Treatments.
444 *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 45, 1662-1667.

445 Goñi, O., Escribano, M.I., Merodio, C. (2008). Gelatinization and retrogradation of
446 native starch from cherimoya fruit during ripening, using differential scanning
447 calorimetry. *LWT- Food Science and Technology*, 41, 303-310.

448 Goñi, O., Fernandez-Caballero, C., Sanchez-Ballesta, M. T., Escribano, M. I., &
449 Merodio, C. (2011). Water status and quality improvement in high-CO₂ treated
450 table grapes. *Food Chemistry*, 128, 1, 34-39.

451 Hinrichs, L. J., Prinsen, M. G., & Frijlink, H. W. (2001). Inulin glasses for the
452 stabilization of therapeutic proteins. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 215,
453 163–174.

454 Hitmi, A., Coudret, A., Barthomeuf, C., & Sallanon, H. J. (2000). Role of intracellular
455 water retention strength in freezing tolerance of *Chrysanthemum cinerariaefolium*
456 Vis. cell cultures. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 157, 47-53.

457 Holland, N., Sala, J. M., Menezes, H. C., & Lafuente, M. T. (1999). Carbohydrate
458 content and metabolism as related to maturity and chilling sensitivity of cv.
459 *Fortune mandarins*. *Journal Agricultural of Food Chemistry*, 47(7), 2513-2518.

460 Imamura, K., Sakaura, K., Ohyama, K., Fukushima, A., Imanaka, H., Sakiyama, T.,
461 Nakanishi, K. (2006). Temperature scanning FTIR analysis of hydrogen bonding
462 states of various saccharides in amorphous matrixes below and above their glass
463 transition temperatures. *Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 110, 15094–15099.

464 Ishiguro. Y., Onodera, S., Benkeblia, N., & Shiomi, N. (2010). Variation of total FOS,
465 total IOS, inulin and their related-metabolizing enzymes in burdock roots (*Arctium*
466 *lappa* L.) stored under different temperatures. *Postharvest Biology and*
467 *Technology*, 56(3), 232-238.

468 Lowithun, N., & Charoenrein, S. (2009). Influence of osmodehydrofreezing with
469 different sugars on the quality of frozen rambutan. *International Journal of Food*
470 *Science and Technology*, 44 (11), 2183-2188.

471 Merchant

472 Miller, D. P., & de Pablo, J. J. (2000). Calorimetric solution properties of simple
473 saccharides and their significance for the stabilization of biological structure and
474 function. *Journal of Physical Chemistry*, 104, 8876–8883.

475 Moraga, G., Martínez-Navarrete, N., & Chiralt, A. (2004). Water sorption isotherms
476 and glass transition in strawberries: influence of pretreatment. *Journal of Food*
477 *Engineering*, 62, 315-321.

478 Muir, J. G., Shepherd, S. J., Rosella, O., Barret, J. S., & Gibson, P. R. (2007). Fructan
479 and free fructose content of common Australian vegetables and fruit. *Journal of*
480 *Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 55, 6619-6627.

481 Nardozza, S., Hallett, I. C., McCartney, R., Richardson, A. C., MacRae, E. A., Costa,
482 G., & Clearwater, M. J. (2011). Is fruit anatomy involved in variation in fruit
483 starch concentration between *Actinidia deliciosa* genotypes?. *Functional Plant*
484 *Biology*, 38, 63-74.

485 Popp, M., & Smirnoff, N. (1995). Polyol accumulation and metabolism during water
486 deficit. In N. Smirnoff (Ed.), *Environment and Plant Metabolism: Flexibility and*
487 *Acclimation*. (pp199-215). Bios Scientific Publishers.

488 Roos, Y. (1993). Melting and glass transitions of low molecular weight carbohydrates.
489 *Carbohydrate Research*, 238, 39-48.

490 Strand, A., Hurry, V., Henkes, S., Huner, N., Gustafsson, P., Per Gardeström, & Stitt,
491 M. (1999). Acclimation of Arabidopsis Leaves Developing at Low Temperatures.
492 Increasing Cytoplasmic Volume Accompanies Increased Activities of Enzymes in

493 the Calvin Cycle and in the Sucrose-Biosynthesis Pathway. *Plant Physiology*, 119,
494 1387-1397.

495 Szepesi, A., Csiszar, J., Gemes, K., Horvath, E., Horvath, F., Simon, L.M., & Tari, I.
496 (2009) Salicylic acid improves the acclimation to salt stress by stimulating
497 abscisic aldehyde oxidase activity and abscisic acid accumulation, and increases
498 Na⁺ content of the leaves without toxicity symptoms in *Solanum lycopersicum* L.
499 *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 166, 914-925

500 Taylor, L. S., & Zografi, G. (1998). Sugar-polymer hydrogen bond interactions in
501 lyophilized amorphous mixtures. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 87(12),
502 1615-21.

503 Torreggiani, D., Forni, E., Guercilena, I., Maestrellia, A., Bertolo, G., Archer, G. P.
504 Kennedy, C. J., Bone, S., Blond, G., Contreras-Lopez, E. & Champion, D. (1999).
505 Modification of glass transition temperature through carbohydrates additions:
506 effect upon colour and anthocyanin pigment stability in frozen strawberry juices.
507 *Food Research International*, 32, 441-446.

508 Valluru, R., & Van den Ende, W. (2008). Plant fructans in stress environments:
509 emerging concepts and future prospects. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 59,
510 2905–2916

511 Wolkers, W. F., Oliver, A. E., Tablin, F., & Crowe, J. H. (2004). A Fourier-transform
512 infrared spectroscopy study of sugar glasses. *Carbohydrate Research*, 339, 6,
513 1077-1085.

514 Zimeri, J. E., & Kokini, J. L. (2002). The effect of moisture content on the crystallinity
515 and glass transition temperature of inulin. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 48, 299-304.
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531 Figure Captions

532 **Figure 1:** HPAEC-PAD chromatography profile of 1-kestose (3a), neokestose (3b),
533 nystose (4c), nystose b (4b) and kestopentaose (5a) extracted from strawberries
534 *Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois after harvest (non-stored, 0 days) and after 3 days of
535 storage at 0 °C in air (air-stored), 20% CO₂ or 40% CO₂. The 1-kestose, nystose and
536 kestopentaose were quantified from the peak area using 1-kestose, nystose and
537 kestopentaose as standard.

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539 **Figure 2:** Content of 1-kestose (A), neokestose (B), nystose (C), nystose b (D) and
540 kestopentaose (E) in strawberries *Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois after harvest (non-
541 stored, 0 days) and after 3 days of storage at 0 °C in air (air-stored), 20% CO₂ or 40%
542 CO₂. The data are presented as the means ± SE of three replicates (n=6) and the
543 different letters indicate significant differences ($p<0.05$).

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545 **Figure 3:** LT-SEM micrographs showing views of cell tissues of fractured strawberries
546 *Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois after harvest (non-stored, 0 days) and after 3 days of
547 storage at 0 °C in air (air-stored), 20% CO₂ or 40% CO₂. Scale bars represent 200 µm.

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549 **Figure 4:** (A) Relationship between T_g and U_w , where (■) includes glucose, fructose,
550 sucrose, maltotriose and maltotetraose, and (▲) includes glucose, fructose, sucrose, 1-
551 kestose, nystose and kestopentaose. (B) Relationship between U_w and the number of
552 furanose rings from various saccharides including FOS (1-kestose, nystose and
553 kestopentaose). (C) Relationship between T_g and ν_{OH} from glucose, trehalose,
554 maltotriose, maltotetraose, fructose, sucrose, raffinose, 1-kestose, nystose and
555 kestopentaose. (D) IR region of the OH stretching region of sucrose ($T_g = 68.29$ °C), 1-
556 kestose ($T_g = 91.16$ °C), nystose ($T_g = 102.17$ °C), kestopentaose ($T_g = 120.85$ °C),
557 illustrating that the maximum of ν_{OH} increases with increasing T_g . All spectra were
558 recorded at 24 °C. Values are the mean of at least three replicate samples ± SE.
559 Thermodynamic data are shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Changes in sugars (mg/g FW), polyols (mg/g FW) or ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW), moisture content (mg/g FW), water Potential (Ψ_w) (MPa), unfreezable water content (g/g DW) and drip loss (%) in strawberries *Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois after harvest (non-stored) and after 3 days of storage at 0°C in air (air-stored), 20% CO₂ or 40% CO₂

	non-stored	air-stored	CO ₂ -treated	
	0d	3d air	3d 20% CO ₂	3d 40% CO ₂
Sugars				
Glucose (mg/g FW)	19.09±2.17 ^a	18.38±2.07 ^a	23.46±2.75 ^b	23.40±2.38 ^b
Fructose (mg/g FW)	19.49±2.26 ^a	19.55±3.03 ^a	23.54±2.61 ^{ab}	24.72±2.54 ^b
Sucrose (mg/g FW)	20.01±2.67 ^b	14.94±1.72 ^a	21.04±2.49 ^b	18.51±2.29 ^{ab}
<i>myo</i> -Inositol (mg/g FW)	0.22±0.23 ^a	0.23±0.28 ^a	0.26±0.46 ^a	0.23±0.93 ^a
D-Sorbitol ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW)	29.31±2.57 ^a	34.17±4.22 ^a	42.76±2.71 ^b	31.36±3.52 ^a
D-Mannitol ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW)	1.16±0.08 ^a	1.79±0.19 ^b	1.55±0.09 ^{ab}	1.23±0.45 ^a
Water status				
Moisture content (mg/g FW)	90.56±0.64 ^a	90.42±0.63 ^a	90.42±0.63 ^a	90.03±0.54 ^a
Water Potential (Ψ_w) (MPa)	-2.60±0.50 ^a	-1.93±0.67 ^a	-2.36±0.78 ^a	-1.06±0.31 ^b
Unfreezable Water Content (g/g DW)	2.67±0.15 ^c	2.21±0.12 ^b	2.67±0.07 ^c	0.79±0.07 ^a
Drip loss 4d at -20°C (%)	1.19±0.06 ^a	3.06±0.05 ^c	1.20±0.02 ^a	2.15±0.06 ^b
Drip loss 9d at -20°C (%)	1.34±0.01 ^a	3.67±0.07 ^d	1.65±0.11 ^b	1.97±0.03 ^c

Data are presented as the means SE of three replicates (n=6).

Table(s)

Carbohydrate	Molecular structure	U _w (mol H ₂ O·mol solute ⁻¹)		T _g (°C)		T _g ' (°C)		ν _{OH} (cm ⁻¹)
		This work	Literature ^a	This work	Literature	This work	Literature	
		Glucose	D-Glc	5.27 ± 0.29	5.0 ^b	35.54 ± 0.84	35 ^d , 38.2 ^e	
Trehalose	α-D-Glcp-(1↔1)-α-D-Glcp	10.17 ± 0.01	10.9 ^c	102.31 ± 0.67	97 ^d , 116.9 ^e	-41.90 ± 0.56	-43 ^c , -42 ^f	3300.85 ± 0.84
Maltotriose	α-D-Glcp-(1↔4)-α-D-Glcp-	13.66 ± 0.25	12.7 ^c	115.23 ± 0.45	110 ^d	-40.37 ± 0.69	-40 ^c	3302.52 ± 0.84
Maltotetraose	α-D-Glcp-(1↔4)-α-D-Glcp-	14.31 ± 0.30	13.3 ^c	134.30 ± 0.14	128 ^d	-39.13 ± 1.55	-38 ^c	3302.81 ± 0.84
Fructose	(1↔4)-α-D-Glcp-(1↔4)-α-D-Glcp- D-Fru	5.44 ± 0.02	5.0 ^b	12.61 ± 1.85	5 ^f	-51.19 ± 1.34	-57 ^f	3271.72 ± 0.84
Sucrose	α-D-Glcp-(1↔2)-β-D-Fruf	7.60 ± 0.28	8.5 ^c	68.29 ± 2.78	73.4 ^e , 62 ^b	-43.30 ± 1.05	-47 ^c , -46 ^f	3288.57 ± 0.84
Raffinose	α-D-Galp(1↔6)-α-D-Glcp-(1↔2)- β-D-Fruf	15.59 ± 0.25	16.2 ^c	116.92 ± 3.71	112.6 ^e , 114 ^h	-51.19 ± 1.34	-40 ^c	3301.92 ± 0.84
1-Kestose	α-D-Glcp-(1↔2)-β-D-Fruf-(2↔1)- β-D-Fruf	17.58 ± 0.14		91.16 ± 4.25		-33.83 ± 0.93		3299.14 ± 0.84
Nystose	α-D-Glcp-(1↔2)-β-D-Fruf-(2↔1)- β-D-Fruf-(2↔1)-β-D-Fruf	18.94 ± 0.22		102.17 ± 0.16		-28.48 ± 1.55		3299.86 ± 0.84
Kestopentaose	α-D-Glcp-(1↔2)-β-D-Fruf-(2↔1)- β-D-Fruf-(2↔1)-β-D-Fruf-(2↔1)- β-D-Fruf	29.02 ± 0.05		120.85 ± 1.72	102 ^g	-26.11 ± 0.15	-26.2 ^g	3304.59 ± 0.84

Table 2- Thermodynamic and structural parameters for aqueous solutions and amorphous matrixes of FOS and other sugars
Values are the mean of at least three replicate samples ± SE.

^a All literature values cited have been estimated in a similar way to the procedure used in the present study.

^b Cited from Furuki *et al.*. (2000).

^c Cited from Furuki *et al.*. (2002).

^d Cited from Imamura *et al.*. (2006).

^e Cited from Miller *et al.*. (2000).

^f Cited from Roos. (1993).

^g Cited from Hinrichs *et al.*. (2001).

^h Cited from Taylor *et al.*. (1998).

Figure 1

Figure 2

FOS: Inulin type

FOS: Inulin neoseris type

□ non-stored

3d air-stored

3d 20% CO₂

3d 40% CO₂

Figure(s)
Figure 3

non-stored

3d air-stored

3d 20% CO₂

3d 40% CO₂

Figure(s)
Figure 4

